

FATIGUE CRACK PROPAGATION STUDIES ON
COMPOSITE MODEL SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

The fatigue crack propagation behavior of model composites consisting of a single fiber bundle in a polymeric matrix has been investigated. Composite materials with a tough thermoplastic polycarbonate matrix show an increase in lifetime by several orders of magnitude, relative to the unfilled matrix material. Final break-down of these samples occurred by matrix and fiber cracking. Composites with a brittle epoxy matrix show a crack stopping effect in the area of the reinforcement bundle. After increasing the load level for several times, final rupture of the samples took place by either matrix cracking along the embedded fiber bundle or by simultaneous matrix and fiber fracture as the main failure mechanism.

INTRODUCTION

Embedding fibers in a polymeric matrix results in a composite material with a very complex mechanical property profile. In Figure 1 those parameters are listed, which can affect their fracture toughness and fatigue crack propagation behavior very strongly: i.e. the mechanical properties of the components used, the bond quality of the fiber/matrix interface, the fiber volume fraction and their orientation with respect to the initial notch.

This study deals with the fracture mechanical behavior of such composites, in particular unidirectionally reinforced model materials. Of special interest was the interaction between a propagating fatigue crack and an embedded fiber bundle, and the effect of matrix ductility and the fiber/matrix bond quality.

Figure 1. Parameters, on which the fatigue crack propagation behavior of composites depend on.

MATERIALS

To study these relationships on a very fundamental basis, two matrices of different fracture toughness, i.e. ductile thermoplastic polycarbonate (PC) and brittle thermosetting epoxy resin (EP) were used. The single fiber bundle reinforcement was performed by the use of three different types of fiber materials:

- a) glass fiber (GF: 3000 filaments, roving cross section area $A = 0.528 \text{ mm}^2$)
- b) carbon fiber (CF: 12000 filaments, $A = 0.462 \text{ mm}^2$)
- c) aramid fiber (AF: 1000 filaments, $A = 0.113 \text{ mm}^2$)

Table 1 represents the composite components, their tradenames and their mechanical properties, as measured in a regular tensile test. This paper presents only the results of fatigue tests on the following composite combinations: PC+GF, EP+GF, EP+CF and EP+AF.

TABLE 1

Mechanical properties of the components used in the composites

Material	Type	Fracture stress [MPa]	Ultimate elongation [%]	Young's modulus [MPa]	Density [g / cm ³]
Polycarbonate PC	Makrolon 3103	66	125.0	2540	1.2
Epoxy-Resin EP	Araldit D	49	7.0	2950	1.1
Carbonfiber CF	Besfight HTA	2990	1.2	238000	1.78
Glassfiber GF	Silenka 1056	1400	1.9	72100	2.56
Aramidfiber AF	Twaron HM	3210	2.3	125000	1.45

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

Manufacturing and Specimen Geometry of the Model Composites

Plaques of model composites were produced by the help of two in principle different procedures. Epoxy and its composites were produced by casting. The plaques were cured in an oven at 60°C for 5h. Figure 2 represents

Figure 2. Hot pressing procedure, which was used for manufacturing PC-composites (schematically P: pressure, F: fiber bundle, V: pretension)

schematically the hot pressing procedure, which was used for manufacturing PC and PC-composite sheets. Two PC-sheets, which one fiber bundle had been fixed, were pressed together at a temperature of 200°C and a pressure of 125 bar for 1h. The result of this procedure is shown in Figure 3 for

Figure 3. GF-bundle, embedded in a PC-matrix

a glass fiber reinforced PC-sample. The shape of the fiber bundles, embedded in an epoxy matrix was more circular, because of the different manufacturing processes.

Compact tension (CT) specimens (Figure 4), with a specimen width

Figure 4: Compact tension (CT) specimen configuration with $W=50.8$ mm and $B = 4$ mm

of $W=50.8$ mm and a thickness of $B=4$ mm, were fabricated from these plaques in a way, that all embedded fiber bundles were arranged parallel to the load line direction.

Fatigue Crack Propagation Tests

Fatigue crack propagation tests were performed at room temperature under load control, using a servo hydraulic testing machine. The applied load was sinusoidal at a minimum to maximum load ratio of 0.2 and a frequency

of 10 Hz. Crack lengths were measured by the use of an optical microscope with a resolution of 0.02 mm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Matrices

In Figure 5 the fatigue curves of the matrix materials are shown. These

Figure 5. Fatigue crack propagation curves of the matrix materials (EP and PC)

curves present the crack propagation rates da/dN vs. the cyclic stress intensity factor ΔK . The calculation of ΔK was performed by using the following relationship:

$$\Delta K = \Delta F/B\sqrt{W} \cdot Y(a/W) \quad (1)$$

where ΔF $\hat{=}$ difference between maximum and minimum load

B $\hat{=}$ specimen thickness

W $\hat{=}$ specimen width

a $\hat{=}$ actual crack length

$Y(a/W)$ $\hat{=}$ geometrical correction factor taken from literature [1]

The resistance against crack propagation is in a higher range for the ductile PC-matrix than for the brittle epoxy resin, that means, that there can be observed a higher crack propagation speed at the same ΔK -level in

EP than in PC. Polycarbonate shows a higher proportion of shear fracture with increasing fatigue crack growth rate, which has been assumed to be due to a transition from a more plane strain to a complete plane stress condition in the zone in front of the propagating crack [2]. Also the discontinuous type of crack growth (area A) changes to continuous crack propagation (area B) at higher ΔK -levels [3]. Figure 6 represents SEM-

Figure 6. Micrographs (SEM) of typical areas of fracture surfaces after fatigue: a) discontinuous crack propagation (Area A in Fig.5); b) continuous crack propagation (Area B in Fig. 5)

micrographs of area A (discontinuous crack propagation) and area B, where a direct correlation between crack propagation (arrest lines) and load cycles exists. In both cases, EP- and PC-matrix, the Paris-equation is valid in the linear range of the fatigue curves [4]:

$$da/dN = C \cdot \Delta K^m \quad (2)$$

with the values:

$m = 6.97$, $C = 1.46 \cdot 10^{-2}$ for EP and

$m = 2.81$, $C = 1.03 \cdot 10^{-4}$ for PC

Composite Model Systems

The same crack speed in the matrix materials was the criterion for the position of the fiber bundles. In both cases the crack propagation rate was about $6.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mm/cycle. So the distance between the fiber bundles and the load line was in the range of 23.5 mm in EP-composites and 28.5 mm in PC-composites. The PC-GF composite specimen shows an increase in lifetime by several orders of magnitude, relative to the neat PC-matrix (Figure 7).

Figure 7. FCP-curve of the glass fiber reinforced PC (PC+GF) compared to the neat PC-matrix (1-6: single steps of crack propagation, see Fig. 8)

The reason for the decrease in crack propagation rates in this system is due to the crack stopping effect by the fiber bundle, which finally results in a crack branching at the bundle, parallel and perpendicular to the load line. This is schematically shown in Figure 8. The crack stops propagating parallel the load line after passing the roving. So locally the individual mechanisms of materials break-down can be subdivided at

Steps of Crack Propagation in PC+GF

Figure 8. Steps of FCP in PC+CF, schematically

first into matrix cracking and fiber/matrix debonding. Final breakdown occurs after fiber cracking of single fibers in the bundle until the total bundle is ruptured. Then, the fatigue crack propagation behavior of this model composites becomes nearly the same as in the pure matrix.

The crack stopping effect by the fiber type hindrance is much more pronounced in the EP-composite systems. The crack completely stops propagating perpendicular to the fiber bundle, in the EP+CF and EP+GF systems even after increasing the load level for several times. Figure 9 represents this for the EP+CF composite system. In the final stage of the fatigue tests all EP-systems show the same fracture mechanisms. After branching of the crack direction associated with fiber/matrix debonding the crack growth rates parallel to the embedded roving dominate (in Figure 9: $\Sigma\Delta a = \Delta a_{\perp} + \Delta a_{\parallel}$; Δa_{\perp} and Δa_{\parallel} : crack growth perpendicular and parallel to the roving). Fracture of these materials takes place by matrix cracking along the fiber bundle.

CONCLUSIONS

The composite materials subjected to fatigue loading conditions show an increase in lifetime by several orders of magnitude, relative to the neat matrices. The most important reason for this effect is the crack

Figure 9. FCP-curve of the carbon fiber reinforced EP compared to the neat EP-matrix; crack growth behavior of EP+CF after increasing the load level ($\Delta F \uparrow$) for several times

branching at the embedded fiber bundles. Final break-down of systems with a tough matrix (PC) occurs by matrix and fiber fracture. In systems with the brittle EP-matrix the crack stops totally at the fiber bundle. After increasing the load level final rupture of the composites occurs by matrix cracking along the fiber bundle.

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